

Supporting information

Slurry Process Optimization through Rheological Investigation for Electrochemical Capacitors

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Table S1 Evolution of yield stress, consistency index and flow index of slurry components at different residence times

Dissolution of CMC in water				
Residence time (min)	τ_0 (Pa)	K (Pa sⁿ)	n	R²
1	0	0.01	0.91	0.9999
5	0	0.03	0.87	0.9997
10	0	0.11	0.81	0.9994
20	0	0.37	0.74	0.9989
30	0	0.59	0.71	0.9987
40	0	0.77	0.70	0.9986
50	0	0.93	0.68	0.9986
60	0	0.94	0.68	0.9985

Dispersion of carbon black				
Residence time (min)	τ_0 (Pa)	K (Pa sⁿ)	n	R²
1	21.09	0.01	1.28	0.6800
5	2.17	0.52	0.75	0.9964
10	0.18	0.79	0.70	0.9990
20	0	0.76	0.69	0.9990
34	0	0.73	0.69	0.9990
48	0	0.78	0.70	0.9990
62	0	0.79	0.70	0.9990
76	0	0.85	0.70	0.9990
90	0	0.86	0.69508	0.9990

Dispersion of activated carbon				
Residence time (min)	τ_0 (Pa)	K (Pa sⁿ)	n	R²
5	34.13	12.96	0.74	0.9997
10	38.02	13.29	0.71	0.9998
20	37.58	13.37	0.69	0.9997
34	33.57	15.09	0.64	0.9997
48	30.95	14.19	0.64	0.9999
62	28.65	14.53	0.63	0.9996
76	27.84	14.06	0.63	0.9999
90	27.33	14.24	0.63	0.9999

Dispersion of SBR				
Residence time (min)	τ_0 (Pa)	K (Pa sⁿ)	n	R²
0	27.33	14.24	0.63	0.9999
5	16.40	15.23	0.60	0.9998
10	15.87	17.15	0.57	0.9998
15	17.35	15.46	0.60	0.9997
20	14.86	15.74	0.57	0.9997
25	18.11	16.02	0.59	0.9998
30	16.52	15.54	0.60	0.9997

Mixing procedures				
Procedure	τ_0 (Pa)	K (Pa sⁿ)	n	R²
Standard	1.83	8.39	0.69	0.9993
Time-optimized	3.40	7.97	0.70	0.9988

Fig. S1 Schematics of Swagelok cell assembly. Adapted from Maurel *et al.* [1]

Fig. S2 Shear stress evolution of slurry components at different residence times and corresponding Herschel-Bulkley fits. **a** Dissolution of CMC in water, followed by the dispersion of **b** carbon black, **c** activated carbon, and **d** SBR. **e** Comparison between standard and time-optimized mixing protocols

Fig. S3 Evolution of yield stress, consistency index and flow index of slurry components at different residence times. **a** Dissolution of CMC in water, followed by the dispersion of **b** carbon black, **c** activated carbon, and **d** SBR. **e** Comparison between standard and time-optimized mixing protocols

Fig. S4 Additional electrochemical performance parameters. **a** Charge-discharge profiles at 50 A g⁻¹, **b** iR drop and **c** internal resistance

References

- [1] Maurel A, Hyeonseok K, Russo R, Grugeon S, Armand M, Panier S, Dupont L (2021) Ag-Coated Cu/Polylactic Acid Composite Filament for Lithium and Sodium-Ion Battery Current Collector Three-Dimensional Printing via Thermoplastic Material Extrusion. *Frontiers in Energy Storage* 9. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2021.651041>